

Effect of UV Radiation on Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles

Ravi L. Dabhade¹, Sachin S. Bhutekar² and Mansi V. Galani³

^{1,2} Assistant Professor, ³ Research Student, Department of Biochemistry,
Shri Shivaji College of Arts, Commerce & Science, Akola, India

Received: May 12, 2025

Accepted: Jun 11, 2025

Published: Jun 13, 2025

ABSTRACT

Silver nanoparticles, also known as AgNPs, are now a commonly used nanomaterial in a variety of industries, including food, medical, and cosmetics. There are three methods of nanoparticles synthesis reported till date including physical, chemical, and biological methods. The current study's goal was to synthesize and characterize Tween 80 capped silver nanoparticles (T80-AgNPs) utilizing a UV radiation reduction approach in light of these significant applications. T80-AgNPs were characterized with a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Surface Plasmon Resonance (SRP) peaks in the 400 nm region were seen in UV-visible spectra. When the length of UV irradiation was increased, it was observed that the intensity of the SPR band of T80-AgNP was increased suggesting that greater yield of T80-AgNPs was achieved.

Keywords: Silver Nanoparticles, Tween 80, UV visible spectrophotometer, surface plasmon resonance [SPR]

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles possess exceptional potential in numerous fields, such as environmental science, agriculture, biomedicine, pharmaceuticals, food technology, and biotechnology. Key attributes of nanoparticles, such as their unique properties, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial effects, biocompatibility, effective drug delivery capabilities, bioactivity, tumor targeting, and bio-absorption, have significantly advanced research in their synthesis and applications in biotechnology and applied microbiology. [1] Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have attracted considerable attention due to their distinctive properties, such as exceptional conductivity, chemical stability, and remarkable optical characteristics. These characteristics have led to the extensive use of AgNPs in various fields, including optical materials, catalysis, and electronics. [2]

The process of creating metal nanoparticles through radiation-induced synthesis has several benefits over conventional methods, such as its simplicity, independence from temperature, ease of process control, uniform reduction and nucleation of nanoparticles, and the absence of reducing agents or unwanted oxidation byproducts. The method of preparing metal nanoparticles has garnered a lot of interest and has demonstrated great promise in controlling particle size and shape by manipulating factors like dose rate, absorbed dose, metal precursor concentration, and the inclusion of stabilizing agents. Furthermore, radiation technique can be utilized to quickly produce larger quantities of materials at the nanoscale, ensuring their suitability for industrial applications. [3]

Surfactant molecules improve the stability of nanomaterials by creating steric hindrance, electrostatic repulsion, van der Waals forces, and other repulsive interactions as they adhere to the surfaces of the nanomaterials. [4] Polyoxyethylene-(20)-sorbitan monooleate, also referred to as Tween 80, is a type of surfactant that is made from polyethoxylated sorbitan and oleic acid. It is commonly utilized in the production of medications, beauty products, and food items. Furthermore, its application in the creation of metallic nanoparticles has been extensively documented. [5] The synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) through γ -irradiation with Tween 80 as a stabilizer, without the need for any chemical reducing agents, has already been carried out and verified using ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy. [2] In recent studies, the impact of ultraviolet radiation on the synthesis of AgNPs has been investigated. The synthesized T80-AgNPs are characterized by UV-visible spectroscopy.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Preparation of reagents

6.25 mm AgNO₃, Tween 80 in 1:200 ratio (0.5 gm Tween 80 in 90 ml deionized water with constant stirring using magnetic stirrer) and isopropyl alcohol is used for preparation of AgNPs.

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles

Five sets were made, each containing 10 ml of 6.25 mM AgNO₃ mixed with 90 ml of tween 80 solution, which is prepared using the same method as before. Each set was blended with continuous agitation. To this, 10 ml of isopropyl alcohol was added as a substance that neutralizes hydroxyl radicals. To achieve a uniform mixture, this prepared solution was stirred continuously for approximately 1 hour.

Exposure of UV to AgNPs

Five out of six sets were subjected to irradiation for 1 hour, 2 hours, 3 hours, and 4 hours using ultraviolet light, while the last set served as a control and was not exposed to the light, remaining at room temperature.

Characterization of T80-AgNPs

After appropriate UV exposure to the samples, a absorption spectrum of T80-AgNPs was noted in the wavelength range of 300-690 nm by means of EI 2375 double beam UV-visible spectrophotometer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 illustrates the absorption spectra of t80-agnps after being exposed to ultraviolet light. The observed color change in the initially transparent solution of T80-Ag⁺ composites, as confirmed by a UV-visible spectrophotometer, indicates the successful synthesis of AgNPs. In the visible light absorption spectrum, the control did not exhibit any visible absorption peaks. Instead, it showed characteristic absorption line similar to the absorption line of sample irradiated by UV light for 1 hr conversely, after UV irradiation for 2, 3, and 4 hours, an absorption peak near 400 nm was clearly observed, corresponding to the Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). This peak is a result of the collective movement of free charge carriers in response to electromagnetic radiation, and its position is affected by the size and shape of the nanoparticles. [06] Typically, the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) observed between 400 nm and 450 nm indicates the synthesis of spherical silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) that are smaller than 30 nm. [10]. Mohamad Bekhit *et.al.*, concluded that the intensity of the SPR band of T80-AgNP increased significantly upon increasing the γ -irradiation dose from 0.5 to 2 KGy. [02] However, we found that the peak intensity of the T80-AgNP SPR band grew slightly as the duration of UV irradiation increased, suggesting that slight greater yields of T80-AgNPs were achieved. It is clear that the variation in color of the mixture containing Tween 80 and silver nitrate from colourless to tan brown corresponds to the increase in optical absorption intensity. It can be concluded that UV irradiation induces slight but consistent amplification in the peak intensity, possibly due to photoreaction needed to generate T80-AgNPs.

It has been demonstrated that the radiation reduction process is an effective way to create highly distributed and monosized metal nanoparticles. Solvated electrons (e_{aq}) and hydrogen radicals (H), the radiolytically produced species from water radiolysis, show significant reduction potentials, which leads to the reduction of silver ions into silver atoms.[8]

The production of T80-AgNPs triggered by UV irradiation has the benefit of producing the necessary strongly reducing radicals without producing any byproducts. On the other hand, HO (hydroxide ion) has the ability to oxidize atoms or ions into higher oxidation states. This is why scavenger of HO radicals, like isopropanol, is typically mixed to solution to stop these oxidations. [9]

Fig 1- Uv-vis absorption Spectra of silver nanoparticles containing 6.25 Mm AgNO_3 and Tween 80 in 1:200 ratio at different UV radiation doses

The present study shows that significant synthesis of silver nanoparticle is observed at 2, 3 & 4 hours incubation of mixture of silver nitrate AgNO_3 and tween 80 in UV radiation. Further we anticipate that sizes of nanoparticles may vary with the time of incubation. This synthesis method for silver nanoparticles can be advantageous for producing nanoparticles with a specific particle size.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Tween 80 was used as a stabilizer throughout the UV radiation process to successfully create Ag nanoparticles without the need for any chemical reduction agents. Regarding the reaction of AgNPs with Tween 80 & the appearance of surface Plasmon resonance, respectively, UV-visible spectrum verified the creation of the T80-AgNPs.

Accordingly, AgNPs are promising for many applications in industry, cosmetics, and food processing and also in pharmaceutical uses.

Acknowledgement

The head of Shivaji College of Arts, Commerce, and Science in Akola is acknowledged by the authors for providing the required equipment and laboratory facilities.

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